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TENTATIVE DESIGN OF THE INTERACTION REGION

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Abstract:

This document summarizes the present design of the interaction region for a 10 TeV center-of-mass muon collider, including the lattice, magnet apertures and shielding configurations.

MuCol Consortium, 2024.

For more information on MuCol, its partners and contributors please see <https://mucol.web.cern.ch/>

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	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	D. Calzolari, M. Vanwelde	CERN	24/10/2024
Edited by	A. Lechner, C. Carli	CERN	24/10/2024
Reviewed by	A. Chance [WP5 Leader] D. Lucchesi [WP2 Leader] M. Lancellotti [Administrative coordinator]	CEA UNIPD CERN	28/10/2024
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Executive summary

The document summarizes the current design of the interaction region for a 10 TeV center-of-mass muon collider, derived in the scope of MuCol. The document first presents the interaction region lattice and corresponding optics functions, followed by a description of the shielding requirements for the superconducting magnets in the final focus region and the adjacent chicane. Finally, the document presents the shielding inserts in the detector region (nozzle) for reducing the beam-induced background.

1. INTRODUCTION

The design of a muon collider poses significant challenges, especially as energy scales reach multi-TeV levels [1]. To achieve a high luminosity, one of the collider's requirements is to tightly squeeze the beams using the final focusing system in the interaction region (very small β -functions at the interaction point). This leads to challenging lattice designs that must also mitigate the effects of radiation from muon decay and beam losses [1-3].

A major concern is the beam-induced background (BIB), particularly from secondary electrons and positrons produced by muon decays, which can perturb the reconstruction of collision events [2-5]. In addition, the secondary particles can give rise to radiation damage in the collider ring magnets and the detector [2-4,6,7]. Effective shielding of magnets around the machine, both in the IRs and in the rest of the machine, is essential to protect components from the radiation load and associated heat deposition [3,6,7]. In addition, nozzle-like conical shielding elements are needed inside the detector to reduce the flux of secondary particles [2-5]. The interaction region design (lattice and shielding elements) must balance performance with durability, minimizing radiation exposure of the machine and detector while enabling the collider performance goals.

This document discusses the most recent advancements in the interaction region design for a 10 TeV center-of-mass muon collider, including shielding strategies for reducing the cumulative radiation damage in magnets and the detector, and for mitigating background levels for physics event reconstruction. The lattice design is an evolution from earlier studies carried out within the International Muon Collider Collaboration (IMCC) [8]. The shielding configuration inside magnets (liners) and the detector (nozzle) has been derived from previous design studies (for 1.5 TeV) performed within the US-Muon Accelerator Program (MAP) [2-3].

Simulations were conducted using FLUKA [9,10], a Monte Carlo code for particle transport in high-energy physics. The simulations provide an estimate of the expected ionizing dose in magnet coils, which can lead to the damage of organic magnet components. In addition, the simulations quantify the beam-induced background in the detector.

2. INTERACTION REGION AND FINAL FOCUS

The primary challenge in designing the interaction region (IR) lattice is meeting the stringent beam dynamics requirements, especially the need for a very small β -function at the interaction point (β^*) to optimize luminosity. Current constraints of the muon collider impose a β^* of 1.5 mm in both the horizontal and vertical planes, matching the bunch length such that luminosity reduction from the hourglass effect starts to become significant [11]. This small β^* results in large beam sizes in the final focus quadrupoles, necessitating extremely high magnetic field strengths in the final focusing triplet.

2.1. LATTICE DESIGN OF THE INTERACTION REGION

As shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2, the interaction region consists of a long drift for the interaction point and detector ($L^* = 6$ m), a triplet for final focusing, a dipolar chicane to mitigate the beam-induced background, and a long straight section where the β -functions are smoothly reduced. The final focus system uses a triplet configuration with two focusing and one defocusing quadrupole. The maximum magnetic field at the magnet aperture is assumed to be 20 T. The first quadrupole is currently divided into shorter segments to maximize achievable gradients while remaining within field limits.

The long straight section in the IR leads to an accumulation of secondary particles from muon decay. In order to remove these particles, a dipolar chicane is included before the final focus triplet, enhancing the separation of decay products. Secondary electrons are deflected more strongly than the primary beam due to their lower energy and smaller mass. Even high-energy decay electrons and positrons quickly lose energy in the dipolar field due to synchrotron radiation. As a consequence, these secondaries are swept across the machine aperture before they can reach the detector region.

Figure 1 Interaction region of the current muon collider lattice design. The interaction region is composed of a long drift for the interaction point ($L^* = 6$ m), a triplet final focus configuration and a chicane to mitigate the beam-induced background.

Figure 2 Lattice functions in the interaction region of the current muon collider lattice design. The small β -functions at the interaction point ($\beta^* = 1.5$ mm) lead to large β -functions in the final focusing triplet and very large chromatic effects that must be compensated in a local chromatic correction section following the interaction region.

2.2. SHIELDING DESIGN FOR MACHINE ELEMENTS

The superconducting magnets in the collider ring must be protected against the heat deposition and cumulative radiation damage due to muon decay in flight. In the presence of magnetic fields, secondary decay electrons and positrons are lost within a few tens of meters on the vacuum aperture. A dedicated shielding strategy has been devised for the magnets in the arc sections (inspired by earlier MAP designs), which incorporates front masks in the interconnects and uniform liners within the magnets [6,7]. A similar approach has been adopted for IR magnets, but differently from the arc section, each liner has a unique profile to adjust the inner aperture to a 5σ beam envelope, where σ is the RMS beam size. By using such a tight physical aperture in the final focus region, decay products are intercepted as much as possible upstream from the IP. This reduces the number of secondary particles, which can reach the detector.

In order to derive the required coil apertures, a generic 1D radial build of final focus quadrupoles was used, which includes different components such as the radiation shielding, supports, thermal insulation and the vacuum chamber (see Table 1). For simplicity, the vacuum aperture is assumed to be round. Considering a tungsten shielding thickness of about 2.5 cm, the inner coil radius amounts to $\max(5\sigma) + 4$ cm, where $\max(5\sigma)$ is the maximum 5σ beam envelope inside the considered magnet. For the dipoles in the chicane, a similar radial build was used, except that the tungsten layer is 2 cm thicker (4.5 cm), which gives a magnet aperture of $\max(5\sigma) + 6$ cm. This increased shielding thickness is needed due to the accumulation of decay products in the upstream straight section, which are lost in the chicane.

For a given quadrupole, the mentioned shielding thickness of 2.5 cm is only the minimum thickness, since the β -function varies strongly along the magnet and hence a thicker shielding can be used where β is smaller (at the IP end of the quadrupoles). This can be realized by using conical shielding liners inside the magnets.

Table 1 Generic 1D radial build of superconducting quadrupoles in the final focus region. The sum defines the inner coil aperture (radius). The table lists the different components, materials, and their respective radial thickness.

Radial Build Component	Thickness
Beam aperture	$\max(5\sigma)$
Coating (Cu)	0.01 cm
Shielding (W)	2.53 cm
Supports and thermal insulation	1.1 cm
Cold bore	0.3 cm
Insulation (Kapton)	0.05 cm
Clearance and liquid helium	0.01 cm
Sum	$\max(5\sigma) + 4$ cm

Particle shower studies with the FLUKA Monte Carlo code [9,10] were carried out in order to quantify the cumulative radiation damage in the different IR magnets. Figure 2 illustrates the adopted geometry model and the radial structure of quadrupoles. The shielding elements for magnets comprise two components, an inner liner constructed from tungsten (as defined by the radial build above) and a front mask located before and after the magnet. These masks protect the superconducting coils from radiation that escapes from the short drift sections between the elements. Additionally, in the drift sections, the beam pipe is surrounded by a tungsten shielding. For the supports and thermal insulation, the material budget has not yet been defined, and we considered vacuum as conservative assumption. Based on this model, the total ionizing dose in coils has been computed for each magnet and is reported in Table 2. The table also lists the different coil apertures. The dose values are given per year of operation, assuming about 140 operational days (1.2×10^7 seconds) per year. The maximum dose is found to be around 8 MGy per year, which is acceptable for 5 years of operation if one considers typical dose limits for insulation materials. However, a thicker shielding might be needed if the number of operational years increases.

Figure 3 FLUKA beamline geometry (left) and the radial build of quadrupoles (right). The point of view in the left figure is from a muon leaving the interaction region and heading towards the arcs. The main components are the tungsten shielding (grey) and the superconducting coils (orange).

Table 2 Radial coil aperture, minimum shielding thickness and yearly total ionizing dose for each magnet in the interaction region.

Magnet in the optics sequence	Length (m)	Shielding thickness (cm)	Inner coil radius (cm)	Annual peak dose in coils (MGy)
IB2	6	4.5	16	1.3
IB1	10	4.5	16	3.1
IB3	6	4.5	16	4.9
IQF2	6	2.5	14	7.7
IQF2_1	6	2.5	13.3	4.6
IQD1	9	2.5	14.5	1.1
IQD1_1	9	2.5	14.5	3.7
IQF1B	2	2.5	10.2	6.4
IQF1A	3	2.5	8.6	3.6
IQF1	3	2.5	7	3.5

2.3. NOZZLE DESIGN FOR BACKGROUND REDUCTION

A nozzle-like shielding inside the detector is essential for reducing the secondary particle flux due to muon decay. A MAP-based nozzle design (from Refs. [2,3]) was used in earlier studies for the 10 TeV collider [4] to validate the simulation framework and to assess the impact of the lattice design on decay-induced background. In subsequent studies, we introduced a slightly adjusted nozzle design with a multi-layered structure. The core is made of INERMET180®, a high-density tungsten alloy with a density of 18 g/cm³, offering easier manufacturability compared to pure tungsten used in previous designs. This core acts as the primary radiation shield, absorbing high-energy particles from muon decays. Surrounding the core is a layer of borated polyethylene, specifically included to moderate and capture neutrons. The outermost layer, also made of INERMET180®, absorbs gamma rays emitted after neutron capture, reducing the low-energy photon background by a factor of 2. The geometric layout of this design is depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Nozzle design for a 10 TeV collider. The nozzle has been adapted from earlier versions designed for 1.5 TeV within MAP [2,3].

3. OPTICS REPOSITORY

The interaction region lattice described in this document can be found in Ref. [12] in the folder *lattice/collider* or in Ref. [13] in the folder *collider/10_TeV*.

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ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
BIB	Beam-Induced Background
IMCC	International Muon Collider Collaboration
IR	Interaction Region
MAP	Muon Accelerator Program (US)
FLUKA	FLUKtuierende KAskade (Monte Carlo particle transport code)